

1 Revisiting biosecurity decisions with hindsight: estimating the 2 realised economic value of a historic medfly eradication

3 **Running head:** Revisiting historic biosecurity actions

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13 Abstract

14 Biosecurity decision-making typically weighs up predicted future outcomes and impacts, but
15 only rarely do we look back to assess and learn from historical decisions. Here, we quantified
16 the contemporary benefits realised from a successful biosecurity action informed by over 100
17 years of subsequent economic data. New Zealand's 1907-08 eradication of invading
18 Mediterranean fruit fly (medfly) incursions facilitated ongoing access to premium fresh fruit
19 markets. Our results estimate cumulative losses to 2020 for apple and kiwifruit exports, had
20 medfly not been eradicated, at 7.6 to 10.2 billion NZD 2022 equivalent. The greatest economic
21 harm would have been loss of market access for kiwifruit exports, which did not even begin
22 until seventy years after the 1907-08 eradications. This example demonstrates massive time-
23 lagged benefits from a biosecurity action and informs the long-term considerations that
24 biosecurity managers regularly face in deciding how to respond to incursions of exotic
25 organisms.

26 Introduction

27 New Zealand is presently a substantial exporter of fresh fruit, especially kiwifruit and apples.
28 These exports are an important part of the New Zealand economy, accounting for over 1% of

29 GDP. The health of this export industry has been, and continues to be, protected by a variety of
30 measures. As an island nation, New Zealand can exercise biosecurity vigilance in the attempt to
31 exclude a variety of pests, pathogens and weeds. One such pest is Mediterranean fruit fly
32 (*Ceratitis capitata*; “medfly”), considered the most economically important fruit fly species ¹, in
33 part because of its ability to survive cooler climates and its ability to inhabit more than 200
34 fruits and vegetables, to which it causes severe destruction and degradation.

35 Medfly probably arrived in New Zealand on 10 October 1906 as infested oranges on the
36 steamship Atua, from Sydney (Australia) via Fiji, Samoa and Tonga ². At the time, the area
37 around Sydney was known to be infested with medfly ³, unlike the South Pacific islands.
38 Although infested fruit imports were previously condemned, lobbying by importers had recently
39 softened the regulations, allowing infested shipments to instead be picked over ⁴. The imported
40 oranges were distributed across New Zealand, and approximately one week later, fruit fly
41 infested oranges were seized in Whangarei, Christchurch, Napier, and Helensville. This led to
42 the previous regulations being re-enacted, abolishing the practice of picking over fruit and all
43 future consignments of fruit infested with fruit fly were to be destroyed ⁵.

44 In January 1907, medfly was found breeding in peaches in several small gardens in Napier ² (Fig.
45 1). In March 1907, medfly was found in peaches on trees in a few local gardens and in a single
46 plot of tomatoes in Springlands, near Blenheim ^{2,6}. Also in March, medfly was found in Napier
47 again, in oranges in a single garden ^{2,7}. Then in January 1908, the following growing season,
48 medfly was found in a nectarine tree in a single, small garden in Devonport, Auckland ^{8,9}. Since
49 import practices had already been tightened, this likely represented an overwintered
50 population from the previous season.

51 The Department of Agriculture responded in each case using the management options
52 available at the time ². These included: (1) notification by growers which established primary
53 sites; (2) inspection of the primary sites and identification of the pest; (3) destruction of infested
54 fruit and kerosene treatment of the soil, as was used in the successful eradication of medfly
55 from Launceston, Tasmania in 1899 ¹⁰; (4) careful examination of nearby properties, with similar
56 extermination activities upon finding the pest; (5) keeping affected places under continual
57 observation; and (6) a public request to report suspected infestations to the Department of
58 Agriculture e.g., ¹¹, which effectively “crowdsourced” early detection of additional sites. These
59 measures were successful and medfly was eradicated from all three sites (Figure 1).

60 In 1921, an incursion of medfly was detected and successfully eradicated from several small
61 orchards near Dargaville ^{12,13}. Since the late 1980s, New Zealand has implemented a structured

62 network of fruit fly surveillance traps ¹⁴ and in 1996 this detected a small incursion of medfly in
63 Mt Roskill, Auckland, which was successfully eradicated ¹⁵. Thanks to the biosecurity measures
64 implemented over the last 120 years New Zealand remains free from economically damaging
65 fruit flies.

66 The absence of fruit flies has been a defining characteristic of New Zealand's horticultural
67 industries. New Zealand exports a wide range of fruit fly susceptible fruits, but here we focus
68 exclusively on apples and kiwifruit which together comprise around 95% of current fresh fruit
69 exports by value ¹⁶. New Zealand started exporting apples in 1910 ¹⁷ and is now the sixth largest
70 exporter of apples by value ¹⁸. Kiwifruit exports started in the 1950s and rapidly surpassed
71 apples to become New Zealand's top fresh fruit export by value and volume. In 2010, New
72 Zealand grown kiwifruit comprised around 30% of the global trade ¹⁹.

73 The 1907-08 medfly eradications and the subsequent success of New Zealand's horticultural
74 exports provide a rare opportunity to evaluate a biosecurity intervention with the benefit of
75 hindsight. Usually, biosecurity losses are calculated into the future based on a contemporary
76 (or future) event. Here we used a different approach, by taking more than a century of
77 experienced economic data as a baseline and considering the likely impacts to date had medfly
78 not been eradicated in 1907-08. We erected counterfactuals representing alternative histories
79 to ask: what was the realised value of that early biosecurity intervention?

80 Results

81 We successfully recreated time series for orchard areas in apples and kiwifruit (Fig. 2). The total
82 area in apples has varied relatively little over the last century apart from a temporary peak in the
83 1990s to around twice the long-term average. In contrast, kiwifruit was developed as a
84 commercial crop in the 1970s and increased rapidly in the early 1980s. Data by land district are
85 available in the Supplementary Note. Inflation-adjusted export earnings from both apples and
86 kiwifruit have increased steadily (Fig. 3), with temporary dips in apple export earnings
87 coinciding with World Wars I and II. Despite the historical importance of apple exports, the
88 kiwifruit export market has been similar to or exceeded the apple market since the mid 1980s,
89 with kiwifruit exports currently earning around three times as much as apples.

90 Benefits of access to premium Tier 1 to 3 markets were greater for kiwifruit than for apples (Fig.
91 4). Historically and on average, Tier 2 countries have generated the greatest unit export returns
92 for both kiwifruit and apples, For 2012 to 2020 there was little difference in mean per unit

93 returns for kiwifruit exported to Tiers 1 to 3, with all these premium markets returning around
94 60% greater value than Tier 4 (rest of the world).

95 Fig. 5 compares the averted losses attributable to fruit fly freedom for kiwifruit (green) and
96 apples (red), under Scenario 1, in which medfly is established nationwide, and Scenario 2, in
97 which it is established only on the North Island. The difference between worst and best case
98 assumptions (the width of the lines) varies considerably by year, but the plots reveal several
99 notable points. First, apple export benefits are small compared to kiwifruit benefits. Second,
100 benefits were negligible before around 1980, even after adjusting for inflation.

101 The comparison between Scenarios 1 and 2 highlights the difference between apple production
102 which is more evenly split between the North and South Islands and kiwifruit production which
103 is mostly concentrated on the warmer North Island. For example, in 2014, the North Island :
104 South Island split was about 2:1 for apples and 19:1 for kiwifruit. As a result, even with
105 production constrained to exportable fruit (by our estimated packout rate), the presence of fruit
106 flies in North Island would have little impact on export apple earnings so long as the South
107 Island is free. In the less restrictive (best) case we project no export losses for apples if the
108 South Island remains fruit fly free, and only small (\$11–\$37 million) losses in the more
109 restrictive (worst) case from 2016 onward. For kiwifruit, however, there was little difference
110 between Scenarios 1 and 2 across both the more and less restrictive cases.

111 Fig. 6 contextualises the benefits of fruit fly freedom within the larger economic impact of New
112 Zealand’s direct export earnings and secondary economic affects. In Scenario 1, economic
113 impacts exceed 0.5% of GDP in the more restrictive case in 2019 and 2020. Scenario 2
114 economic impact, while smaller, is still in the range 0.1%-0.45% of GDP in most years from
115 1985, and always above 0.1% of GDP from 2001 onward.

116 Our analysis conservatively estimates the cumulative benefits up to 2020 of fruit fly freedom to
117 New Zealand as 7.6 to 10.2 billion NZD (2022 equivalent), with around 90% of this arising from
118 the ability of kiwifruit exports to access premium markets (Table 2).

119 Discussion

120 To the best of our knowledge, this study is the first published attempt to retrospectively assess
121 the contemporary economic value of a historical biosecurity eradication. Biosecurity risk
122 analysis and incursion response involve prediction of future outcomes and impacts, but rarely
123 do we look back to assess and learn from decisions made long ago. New Zealand’s 1907-08

124 medfly eradication provides a compelling example, because the country's ongoing status of
125 fruit fly freedom has been a defining quality of its horticultural industries for over a century^{20,21}.

126 Any kind of counter-factual analysis is challenging, and our analysis made some assumptions
127 that are open to debate. For example, importing countries could be placed into tiers differently.
128 By considering best and worst cases for each scenario, we have tried to provide an indicative
129 range where certain key markets are uncertain. The addition of a few smaller markets into
130 affected tiers would make only a small difference to our results. Generally, the inclusion of
131 additional markets into our trade affected tiers would only increase the estimated benefits of
132 fruit fly freedom.

133 We conservatively assumed that fruit flies would cause no yield losses from direct damage to
134 crops. From a practical point of view, this means that we do not need to model the extent,
135 pattern and rate of medfly spread following the 1907 incursion, which would be difficult and
136 introduce much uncertainty. The experience of other medfly-established regions is that yield
137 losses due to medfly are small because it can be controlled cheaply and effectively²². In part,
138 this can be attributed to the success of organophosphate insecticides which can achieve near
139 100% control when used properly but which are now being phased out in many countries²³. In
140 addition, kiwifruit appears to be a poor ovipositional host and a poor developmental host for
141 medfly²⁴. Experiments suggest external hairs play a role, along with fruit chemistry (e.g., acidity,
142 amino acids, fatty acids, flavonoids, phenolic acids, etc.)²⁵.

143 We conservatively assumed additional costs for controlling medfly would be zero. Insecticide
144 controls were already used for pipfruit to control pests (e.g., tortricid leafrollers, codling moth,
145 lightbrown apple moth, San Jose scale, woolly apple aphid and European red mite)^{21,26}.
146 Similarly, they were used for kiwifruit following the start of exports to control pests (i.e.,
147 leafroller, scale)²⁷. We also conservatively assume other costs (e.g., phytosanitary costs,
148 damage to health and well-being, damage to native flora and fauna) are also zero.

149 It is important to note that, following Weitzmann²⁸, we did not use a discount rate in this work.
150 Given the length of the time horizon, hyperbolic discounting with rates that progressively and
151 quickly move to zero also would not substantially change our results. Discounting is normally
152 used by economists to value different and predictable streams of benefits and costs over a
153 relatively short period of time. This does not apply to our case study. Over very long time
154 horizons, it is justifiable to use a zero, a very low, or even a negative discount rate and certainly
155 so with environmental and potentially inter-generational assets²⁹. In other words, the decision
156 to eradicate medfly is not seen as a 'business decision' in 1907 since no one could have

157 anticipated, much less predicted or estimated, the inter-generational benefit to New Zealand
158 from having a vibrant fresh pipfruit and kiwifruit industry in place today. Indeed, discounting a
159 flow of benefits - or costs for that matter, think of the impacts of global warming on future
160 generations - over more than a century in the future would be worth near zero in 1907 at any
161 standard discount rate. But, again, this would ignore the substantial inter-generational benefit
162 in place in New Zealand today.

163 Other historical biosecurity actions could be scrutinised in a similar way. Some were
164 successful, such as the 1899 eradication of medfly from Tasmania¹⁰ and ongoing freedom from
165 this pest which continues to benefit the island's fruit industries³. Similarly, apple codling moth
166 *Cydia pomonella* has been repeatedly eradicated from Western Australia since 1903
167 (<https://b3.net.nz/gerda>). Sometimes costly early failures have been turned around. For
168 example, early attempts to eradicate the spongy moth (*Lymantria dispar*) from North America
169 failed³⁰, but since 1992 an active campaign to "slow the spread"³¹ has accrued substantial
170 benefits from delaying the need to remove and replace residential trees³², which can be very
171 costly³³. Similarly, failed attempts from 1907 to 1968 to eradicate citrus whitefly *Dialeurodes*
172 *citri* from California incurred significant costs but have been rendered moot by the success of
173 modern biological controls³⁴. Other early biosecurity actions led to unforeseen outcomes. For
174 example, attempts to eradicate medfly from Bermuda started in 1907, but success was not
175 achieved until 1963³⁵. Meanwhile, the insectivorous lizard *Anolis grahami* had been introduced
176 to Bermuda as a biological control for medfly but proved unsuccessful except in hampering
177 later introductions of Coccinellid beetles to control scale insects³⁶.

178 Biosecurity managers regularly face decisions on how to respond to incursions of exotic
179 organisms, most often under considerable uncertainty. The decision on whether or not to
180 attempt eradication can be problematic because the costs and benefits may be hard to
181 evaluate and the decision itself is asymmetric: by choosing not to eradicate, managers are
182 accepting potential damages from the organism in perpetuity; but attempting eradication may
183 be costly³⁷, may have uncertain success, and may achieve only temporary relief until the next
184 incursion occurs.

185 New Zealand's 1907-08 medfly response illustrates that biosecurity decisions may have long-
186 term ramifications. Despite addressing uncertainty with probably over-conservative
187 assumptions, we conclude that New Zealand's freedom from economically significant fruit flies
188 has been worth at least \$NZ 7.6 billion (2022 dollars) cumulatively in avoided direct costs.
189 However, the commitment to excluding medfly and other fruit flies from New Zealand also
190 incurred costs. It is no longer possible to estimate the economic cost of implementing medfly

191 eradications in 1907-08 and 1921, but the 1996 eradication cost more than NZ\$5 million²⁰. In
192 addition, New Zealand funds an extensive trapping programme for early detection and to prove
193 freedom from fruit flies¹⁴. Nevertheless, it seems clear that the costs of these measures are
194 dwarfed by their sizeable economic benefits. Particularly striking are the benefits to the kiwifruit
195 industry, which did not even come into being until seventy years after the 1907-08 eradications.
196 This example shows that successful biosecurity actions can, in some cases, yield unimagined
197 benefits for centuries to come. New Zealand's horticultural industries owe a debt of gratitude to
198 the early pioneers of biosecurity, and to those whose work continues to exclude exotic fruit flies
199 from the country.

200 Methods

201 We sourced historical datasets for orchard area, fruit production by volume and value, exports
202 by country, Consumer Price Index (CPI) and Gross Domestic Product (GDP) annually for the
203 period 1907 to 2022. Some data were available both regionally (using the standard districts
204 shown in Fig. 1) and nationally, allowing for cross-validation and extrapolation of missing
205 values. Data were recovered from a range of sources, most notably the New Zealand Official
206 Yearbook ([https://www.stats.govt.nz/indicators-and-snapshots/digitised-](https://www.stats.govt.nz/indicators-and-snapshots/digitised-collections/yearbook-collection-18932012/)
207 [collections/yearbook-collection-18932012/](https://www.stats.govt.nz/indicators-and-snapshots/digitised-collections/yearbook-collection-18932012/)) and the Statistics New Zealand Infoshare
208 database (<https://infoshare.stats.govt.nz/>). Full data sources and analysis methods are
209 detailed in the Supplementary Note.

210 Figure 7 summarises our methods. From the historical data we developed three families of
211 complete time series over the years 1907– 2020 for apples and kiwifruit separately: (1) orchard
212 area by land district; (2) New Zealand fruit production volumes; and (3) fruit volume available
213 for export. Separately we used country-specific data to determine the yearly distribution of
214 apple and kiwifruit exports to individual countries. Together, these data allowed us to feign
215 reduced regional production or restricted export markets for fruit as scenarios for the potential
216 impacts of medfly, had it established.

217 Export markets were classified into four tiers (Table 1). Tier 1 comprised premium markets
218 identified in a market analysis for Western Australian fruit¹⁸. Tiers 2 and 3 captured markets
219 where trade was impacted in response to the 1996 medfly incursion or where a strict
220 biosecurity regimen is in place. We assumed that Tier 1 and 2 markets would be impacted by
221 the presence of medfly in New Zealand. We were less certain about the impacts on Tier 3
222 markets, so considered best and worst cases. For example, China is a large export market and
223 by placing it in Tier 3 we considered the situations where there are and are not additional trade

224 restrictions. Tier 4 comprised all other markets, for which we assume no trade impacts from
225 fruit fly presence.

226 We considered two scenarios depending on whether medfly is present throughout New Zealand
227 (Scenario 1) or only in North Island (Scenario 2). Scenario 2 might have been possible through
228 internal quarantine, noting that ecoclimatic models suggest South Island to be less suitable for
229 medfly than the North³⁸. In best cases, only Tier 1 and 2 markets are impacted for fruit exported
230 from medfly areas; in worst cases, Tiers 1, 2 and 3 are impacted (Table 1). Where a Tier is
231 affected, we assumed the fruit would be redirected to other markets, and that the unit price
232 (i.e., dollars per tonne) for the fruit is the lesser of the unit price for that Tier and Tier 4
233 (calculated yearly). Where the Tier 4 unit price is lower (the usual case), a loss is created.

234 Other than the presence of medfly, all other factors were held to be historically similar.
235 Explicitly, we assumed the following.

236 1. The only economic impact of medfly presence is on market access; yield losses and
237 additional costs are assumed to be zero. This is a conservative assumption but partly reflects
238 New Zealand's history of successful innovation in horticultural pest management.

239 2. Orchard area trends for apples and kiwifruit would be unchanged. As relatively high-value
240 crops, it is reasonable to assume that kiwifruit and apples would remain economically
241 attractive crops even at the lower returns available from Tier 4 markets. Replacement of
242 kiwifruit and apples with lower value crops would lead to even greater impacts of medfly on the
243 economy.

244 3. Total exported fruit in a scenario is the same as historical. This arises from the previous two
245 assumptions.

246 4. Fruit that would otherwise have sold in premium markets (Tiers 1 to 3) is redirected and sold
247 at the lesser unit price of that Tier and Tier 4. Therefore, redirected fruit can create a loss and
248 never creates a gain. The assumption that Tier 4 markets would absorb any extra fruit leads to a
249 conservative estimate for the benefits of medfly freedom because not selling the extra fruit
250 would lead to even greater losses compared to the current situation.

251 5. Access to premium markets could not be secured through disinfestation treatments without
252 significant economic burden. Essentially, we assume that the costs of implementing
253 disinfestation would exceed the price benefits offered by those premium markets that might
254 allow it. Effective disinfestation technologies were not available for much of our timeframe, and

255 chemical fruit treatments might also endanger New Zealand’s “clean and green” reputational
256 advantage.

257 6. We do not model price elasticities because there are insufficient data for our timeframe.
258 Additional fruit selling into Tier 4 markets could depress prices and further reduce returns for
259 New Zealand growers, so ignoring price elasticity leads to conservative results.

260 7. In Scenario 2 we do not allow for land use shifts between North and South Islands to
261 compensate for medfly presence in the North. While feasible for apples, few areas in South
262 Island are climatically suitable for growing kiwifruit.

263 8. New Zealand would still invest in fruit fly surveillance and prevention. There would be no
264 savings in border management costs if medfly were present, since biosecurity authorities still
265 try to exclude other pests.

266 Good quality data on orchard areas, production, exports, and returns were available only for the
267 period 1964-2020, which nonetheless comprised almost all export activity. A lack of early
268 kiwifruit trade data was addressed by extrapolation and direct trade losses were scaled to
269 wider impacts on the New Zealand economy using a multiplier of 2.14, as described in the
270 Supplementary Note.

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280 Author contributions

281 This study was conceived by AF and JK and developed together by all authors. DR and AF
282 sourced the historical data and DR conducted the analysis. All authors (DR, JK, AF, TK and AR)
283 contributed to writing and reviewing the manuscript. JK managed submission and revisions.

284 **Competing interests**

285 The authors declare no competing interests.

286 **Data availability**

287 The datasets used during the current study are publicly available, as detailed and hyperlinked
288 from the Supplementary Note. They may also be requested from the corresponding author.

289

290 **Tables**

291 **Table 1.** Market access tiers, showing which markets can (Yes) and cannot (No) be accessed
 292 under Scenarios 1 (medfly present throughout NZ) and 2 (medfly present only in North Island; NI
 293 = exports from North Island, SI = exports from South Island).

Definitions		Scenario 1		Scenario 2			
Tier	Export market	Worst case	Best case	Worst case		Best case	
				NI	SI	NI	SI
1	Hong Kong, India, Malaysia, Oman, Taiwan, Vietnam	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes
2	Japan, South Korea, Tonga, Fiji	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes
3	China, Australia, United States	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
4	All other countries/regions	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

294

295

296 **Table 2.** Millions of 2022 New Zealand dollars of losses accumulated from 1964–2020.

297 Percentages are expressed relative to export values for each commodity, and combined, for the
 298 same period. Under Scenario 1 medfly are assumed present throughout NZ; in Scenario 2 they
 299 are only present in North Island.

Scenario	Case	Apples (%)	Kiwifruit (%)	Total (%)
1	Best case	460.8 (1.9)	7,223.0 (16.9)	7,683.8 (11.4)
1	Worst case	958.7 (3.9)	9,227.0 (21.6)	10,185.8 (15.1)
2	Best case	0.0 (0.0)	6,098.3 (14.3)	6,098.3 (9.0)
2	Worst case	92.0 (0.4)	8,018.8 (18.7)	8,110.9 (12.0)

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303

304 **Figure 1.** Map of New Zealand showing standardized cadastral land districts used for analysis
305 and the approximate locations of medfly incursions. The Auckland district combines a number
306 of historical districts; Gisborne was a separate district from 1923.

307

308 **Figure 2.** New Zealand orchard areas estimated for apples (red), kiwifruit (green) and all fruits
 309 (blue). Complete data are indicated by filled circles, while empty circles show data obtained by
 310 modelling or interpolation.

311

312

313 **Figure 3.** Total New Zealand export earnings for apples (red) and kiwifruit (green).

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315

316 **Figure 4.** Realised mean value of kiwifruit (left) and apple (right) exports to premium Tier 1, 2
 317 and 3 markets, relative to the mean value of Tier 4 markets.

318

319

320 **Figure 5.** Estimated annual benefits of fruit fly freedom for New Zealand’s kiwifruit (green) and
 321 apple (red) exports. Line width indicates the difference between best and worst case estimates.

322

323

324 **Figure 6.** Estimated economic impacts of fruit fly freedom for New Zealand’s kiwifruit and apple
 325 exports as a proportion of GDP. Line width reflects the difference between best and worst case
 326 estimates. Direct export earnings are extrapolated to wider economic impacts using a
 327 multiplier of 2.14, based on Underwood ²⁰.

328

329

330 **Figure 7.** Illustration of how historical data (ovals) were used to estimate the counterfactual
 331 and infer export earnings from kiwifruit and apples had fruit flies been present in New Zealand.

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